

Socio-Cultural Constraints Faced by Girls Regarding Access to their Secondary Education in Mardan, Khyber Pakhtunkhuwa

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Abstract

The study was aimed to explore the socio-cultural constraints (SCCs) faced by girls regarding access to secondary education (SE) in Mardan District, Khyber Pukhtoonkhuwa for which a five point likert type rating scale, consisted of 36 items was developed by following the systematic procedure. The value of Alpha Reliability coefficient was .722. A sample of one hundred and twenty (120) girls with the age limit of fifteen to thirty five (15-35) was taken through snow-ball sampling technique. Parent's education, and family income were the demographic variables of the research. The data after analysis demonstrated that girls in Mardan are far behind in education because of the distance from schools, family permission, low family income, sexual harassment, purdah restrictions, preference of male education over female education, concept of honor, early marriages, lack of awareness regarding the importance of female education, wrong perception about the investment on female education and inferior position of females in the society. It has been recommended that comprehensive awareness raising programs may be incorporated at community level to promote positive attitude among the community regarding the girl's education.

1.1. Introduction

When seen minutely; Pakistan is facing and going through much turmoil that leads to the continuous breaking of walls and weakening the roots of the state. It is quiet unfortunate to mention that our problems are self created and we, as a society still cannot focus on the ways that helps in sorting out the present problems and constraints faced in almost every institution even after so many years of independence and freedom. We, as a nation have made our institutions weak and un-pure from inside as by following the dominating discriminatory rules, regulations and our fore father's practices. These discriminatory and oppressive practices are deep rooted in the system that has now taken place in the skin of our brains and foundations of our psychology as a nation. These practices are leading to the neglect of one complete section of the society who are not a minority, they are the unfortunate "girls and women" who are the victims, sufferers and more modernly are the survivors of this misbalanced structure.

One example of this neglect can be seen in field of education where girls are dropped out of the schools, colleges and universities due to many SCCs (socio-cultural constraints) issues. Naseem (2006) stated that in Pakistan; girls or female education is being hurdalized socio-culturally and economically. According to the report of World Bank Group (1996); there are thousands of SCCs towards girls' education at different levels that can be categorized into two major sections; first of which is known as DCs (Demand Constraints) and second is known as SCs (Supply Constraints) that are closely interwoven. DCs means all the expectation from education system and society as a whole along with government sector in it accordingly as it consists of three sections in it i.e. individual level, family level and community level. Where as SCs are the lacking and shortcomings in education system from the state or government side i.e. they include the list of those facilities that are not provisioned by the state or government towards education section. The effects of these factors on

girls' education are far-reaching, and affect the performance and persistence of those girls who remain in schools.

It has been investigated by Lloyd et al. (2007) that the basic factors becoming a hurdle in female's education includes poverty and parental concerns regarding the safety and mobility of their daughters and under-investment in girls' schooling for which students should be provided with free curriculum and fee concession policies should be introduced.

By keeping in view the above mentioned scenario the present study has aimed to find out the socio-cultural constraints faced by girls of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa because that is apparently and factually a totally different, dynamic and extremely rigid district which is actually the results and effects of "Talibanization" and "the apparent practices of wrong Islamic values". The focus will be on access to secondary level of education as this stage of the life is the most important boost up years in one's life and hurdles in the access to their education can lead to many problems in future that when combined might act as a vicious cycle of problems leading to many other streams of hurdles that eventually ends into disastrous effects.

Methodology

2.1 Objectives of the study:

- To find out socio-cultural constraints faced by girls regarding access to secondary education.
- To find out the effect of parents' education on socio-cultural constraints faced by girls regarding access to secondary education.
- To find out the effect of family income on socio-cultural constraints faced by girls regarding access to secondary education.

2.2. Operational Definitions

- **Socio-cultural constraints:** Hurdles that are related to both social and cultural matters i.e. both society and culture does not allow anything against the set patterns thus creating barriers for the un- acceptable phenomenon.
- **Secondary education:** In the present research SE is the education level from grade nine (9th) up-till intermediate (FA.FSC). Whereas ninth and tenth (9th and 10th) is certified as "matriculation" (SE) and eleventh and twelfth (11th and 12th) is certified as "intermediate" (higher SE) so basically it contains two sections in one frame.

2.3. Research Design

Quantitative research design was used for which a five point likert type rating scale (socio-cultural constraints scale, SCCS) consisted of 36 items was designed in first phase of the study, by following a systematic procedure. It was further divided in two main categories supply and demand constraints, where the second category consisted of three sub-categories individual level, family level and community level constraints. Alpha reliability (.72) was established through pilot testing.

2.4. Sample

The sample consisted of one hundred and twenty (120) girls who had not been able to complete their secondary education and the age limit was from fifteen to thirty five (15-35) years. Snow ball sampling of non-probability sampling technique was used to select the participants/sample.

Results

Table 1

Categorization of Percentile Ranks (Low, Moderate and High level of constraints) and Corresponding Frequencies & Percentages (N= 120)

Categories	Percentiles	F	Percentages
Low	Up to 25 th	33	21.5%
Moderate	Between 25 th &75 th	58	54.5%
High	75 th and above	29	24%
Total		120	100

Table no 1 presents the frequencies and percentages of low, moderate and high scores of the SCCs faced by girls regarding access to their SE in Mardan District. In total 21.5% girls are experiencing low level of SCCs faced regarding access to their SE. 54.5% girls are experiencing moderate level of SCCs while 24% girls are experiencing high level of SCCs for access to secondary education.

Table 2*Percentages of five response categories of SCs Category of SCCS*

No	Items	Strongly disagree %	Disagree %	Uncertain %	Agree %	Strongly agree %
1	Lack of institution	19.2	50.8	6.7	12.5	10.8
2	Lack of transport facilities	23.5	37.5	0.6	26.7	11.7
3	Lack of single-sex institutes	36.5	25	5.8	18.5	14.2
4	Distance of schools from home	10	25.8	5.8	41.7	16.7
5	Lack of female teachers	19.2	37.5	6.7	25.8	10.8
6	Lack of free curriculum	13.3	5	5.8	31.7	44.2
7	Lack of water facilities	21.7	29.2	8.1	25	16
8	Lack of fee concession	15	20.8	9.2	27.5	27.5

Results in table 2 presents' percentages of five response categories on SCC's questionnaire. In the above table of SC the high percentages on agree and strongly agree responses are on item no 6, 4 & 8. The high percentage on disagree and strongly disagree responses are on item no 1, 3 & 2 where as the high percentage on undecided response is on item no 8 only.

Table 3*Percentages of five response categories of DCs: First Sub-Category of SCCS*

No	Items	Strongly disagree %	Disagree %	Uncertain %	Agree %	Strongly agree %
1	Respondent desire of education	14.2	7.5	2.5	32.5	43.3
2	Permission of education from family	37.5	27.5	6.7	15.8	12.5
3	Low income of respondent family	7.5	26.7	3.3	37.5	25
4	Sexual harassment	2.5	18.3	13.3	35	3.9
5	Purdah restrictions	8.3	13.3	7.5	24.2	46.7

6	Lack of scholarship	8.3	20	23.3	35.8	12.5
7	Burden of educational expenditure	9	23	9	23	36
8	Lack of permission to study in other city	22.5	12.9	40	10	10.8
9	Interpretation of Islamic concept regarding girls education	10.8	25.8	19.2	32.5	11.7

Results in table 3 presents' percentages of five response categories of individual level sub-category of DCs category, on SCCS. High percentages on agree and strongly agree responses are on item no 1, 5, 4, 2 & 3. The high percentages on disagree and strongly disagree response is on item no 9 only where as the high percentage on undecided response category is on item no 8 .

Table 4

Percentages of five response categories of DCs: Second Sub-Category of SCCS

No	Items	Strongly disagree %	Disagree %	Uncertain %	Agree %	Strongly agree %
1	Preference of boys education over girls education	3.9	11.9	10	17.5	56.7
2	Preference of informal education over formal education	2.5	13.3	8.3	44.2	31.7
3	Concept of honor	2.5	8.3	9.2	49.2	30.8
4	Lack of awareness regarding importance of education for girls	4.2	16.6	9.2	36.7	33.3
5	Early marriages of girls timing of schools	8.3	16.7	3.4	23.3	48.3
6	Responsibility of domestic chores	3.3	22.5	6.7	31.7	35.8
7	Society pressure on family for girls education	5.8	26.7	15.8	30.8	21.7
8	Effect of parents low education	10.8	20	2.6	28.3	38.8
9	Dependency of women on family	8.3	14.2	10.8	32.5	34.2

Results in table 4 presents' percentages of five response categories of family leve sub-category of DCs category, on SCCS. High percentages on agree and strongly agree responses are on item no 3, 2, 5, 1, & 4. The high percentages on strongly disagree and disagree responses are on item no 6 & 8 where as the high percentage on undecided response is on item no 9 only.

Table 5

Percentages of five response categories of DCs: Third Sub-Category of SCCS

No	Items	Strongly disagree %	Disagree %	Uncertain %	Agree %	Strongly agree %
1	Wrong perception about women education	5	8.3	15.8	31.7	39.2
2	Inferior position of women in society	1.7	10.8	6.7	53.3	27.5
3	Women role of bearing an rearing child	0.8	4.2	20	43.3	31.7
4	Role of religious parishioners	14.2	25.8	18.3	27.5	14.2
5	Feudalism in society	17.6	35.8	15.8	20.8	10
6	Concept regarding education expenditure on women in society	12.5	28.3	10.9	27.5	20

Results in table 5 presents' percentages of five response categories of community level sub-category of DCs category, on SCCS. High percentages on agree and strongly agree responses are on item no 2 & 1. The high percentage on strongly disagree and disagree response is on item no 3 where as the highest percentage on undecided response is on item no 3 only.

Table 6

ANOVA shows the difference in socio-cultural constrains faced by girls on the basis of their family income on SCCS (N=120)

SCCS	1000-10,000 n=85		11,000-20,000 n=12		21,000-above n=23		F
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	
	118.3	12.20	119.4	9.922	118.4	11.94	.044

$df= 118, * p < 0.05$

The findings in table 6 indicate significant difference in socio-cultural constrains faces by girls on the basis of their family income.

Discussion

The present study was carried out to investigate and analyze the socio-cultural constraints faced by girls regarding access to their secondary education in Mardan District. Percentile ranks were computed and results showed (see table1) 54.5% participants fall between 25th and 75th percentile while 24% fall against 75% and above percentile. This indicates that a high number of participants faced constrains for access to secondary education. Most commonly reported constrains, in SCs category (see table no 2) were distance from schools; lack of free curriculum or books facilities and lack of fee concession which were considered contributing factors for low level of enrollment and high dropout rates of female students. Similar issues have been identified in the research presented by Jacobs, (1996) states that girl's education in many areas of the world is basically facing problems like the distance of the institutions as long traveling is not appreciated by many societies because of the security reasons as it might lead to non-secure incidents therefore, girls are restricted to travel too far. According to the study of Government of Pakistan on National Education Policy, (2009); the issues of limited access to fees and school expenditure due to poverty were highlighted. Another study presented by Goel (2004), stated that lack of financial resource is the fundamental reason that is acting as a hurdle in education of girls.

Response analysis for DCs (see table 3, 4 & 5) category revealed that although respondents have a strong desire to attain SE but due to traditions they have faced constraints such as purdah restrictions, lack of scholarship and burden of school expenditures, preference factors, sexual harassment, child marriages, early pregnancies and the negative attitude of the society towards girl's education. literature [Yeoman (1987), Parveen (2008), and Rihani (2008)] also proved that mostly parents do not allow their daughters to indulge themselves in educational activities as they are influenced by the societal pressure. The practice of early marriages of girls is also a contributing factor as the general society thinks that as the girl child will be transferred to someone else on the name of marriage and eventually she will have to perform reproductive and domestic responsibilities so it is considered useless to spend on girl's education.

The findings also highlighted some of the aspects that are not considered as an issue or problem in the respective area where the study took place. As according to the respondents; lack of institutions, lack of single-sex institutes, and lack of transport facilities, feudalism and interpretations of Islamic concepts regarding female education are not the major contributing factors regarding the access to SE in Mardan District. This was because there are plenty of institutes in the specified area, and single-sex schooling prevails basically as the respective culture and societal norms do not allow both men and women to interact together in any institution so there is no co-education after fourth grade in most of the schools. There is no issue of transport facility in the respective area as still there prevails the transports like rickshaws and tangaa'z to a great extent and that is cheap as well. Feudalism and interpretation of Islamic concepts regarding female education was also not considered the main issue or contributing factors for SCCs regarding girl's access to SE. Participants responded negatively when they were inquired about the effect of issues like the responsibility of domestic chores and women's role of bearing and rearing a child which depicts the strong acceptance of these social roles.

Lastly, ANOVA was computed to analyze the effect of family's monthly income and SCCs faced by girls' regarding access to SE (see table 6). Significance of results proved that for the families with low income it is difficult to afford the expenses of education and if so then the preference is mostly given to boy's education as they are supposed to support the family in future for which they must be properly trained while on other hand girls are suppose to move to another family after marriage, so investment on them will not give in return to the current family. This phenomenon is supporting the set patterns of patriarchal structure of Mardan District.

Conclusion:

Findings of the research showed that the girls were not allowed to step out of their domestic spheres without the permission of any male member of their family may it be younger brother, father, fiancé or husband where majority of them negate the idea of female/girls education. Strict purdah restrictions were imposed on the girls of Mardan District from the age of puberty. The findings also showed that heavy domestic liabilities, responsibilities and early marriages were adding to the constraints of girl's education. Male dominancy as the respondents confessed that they could not do anything alone in this regard because the power to make decisions mainly rest with the males. General perception is that to educate girls was not an advantage and the money spent or investment for girls education was a wastage as there was no financial benefit in educating the females or girl child. Preference of male education, the issue of sexual harassment, lack of financial facilities provided by the government, wrong societal perception regarding female education and socio-economic factors were the problems faced by girls of the respective area.

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